

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MORNA****FIRST NAME: EMMANUEL****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. How does the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) approach using block quotations in academic writing compare to other style guides?
 - CMS recommends block quotes for passages of 50 words or more.
 - CMS suggests using block quotes only for poetry or dramatic dialogue.
 - CMS advises that quotes of 100 words or more or at least eight lines.¹**
 - CMS discourages the use of block quotes in favor of paraphrasing.
2. How do you handle multiple references to the same source in Chicago-style footnotes?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2024), 49.

- Use “ibid.” for all subsequent references.
 - Repeat the full citation for each reference.
 - Use “op. cit.” followed by the page number.
 - Provide a shortened reference with the author’s name, short title, and page number.²**
3. In notes-bibliography style, how should you cite a work with no author in the bibliography?
- List it under “Anonymous.”
 - List it under its title.³**
 - Omit it from the bibliography.
 - List it under its publisher.
4. How should you handle a quotation within a quotation in your text?
- Use double quotation marks for both.
 - Use single quotation marks for both.
 - Use double quotation marks for the outer quotation and single for the inner.⁴**
 - Italicize the inner quotation.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2024), 54.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago: Chicago University Press, 2018), 174.

⁴ Ibid., 372.

5. How should you handle a quotation that contains a misspelling?
- Correct the spelling without comment.
 - Insert [sic] after the misspelled word.**⁵
 - Correct the spelling and add a footnote.
 - Leave the misspelling as is without comment.
6. What is the primary purpose of the dissertation concept paper?
- To present the final research findings.
 - To obtain funding for the research.
 - To defend the completed dissertation.
 - To explore a potential dissertation research study.**⁶
7. What is the recommended approach for organizing the discussion of findings in Chapter 5?
- By themes that emerged from the data.
 - In chronological order of data collection.
 - By research questions and hypotheses (Research Questions and Hypotheses).**⁷
 - By level of statistical significance.

⁵ Ibid., 375.

⁶ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2018), 2.

⁷ Ibid., 56-58.

8. Which system of units has been adopted for science and technology in the European Union?
- Imperial system.
 - US customary units.
 - CGS system.
 - International System of Units (SI).**⁸
9. How should items in a list consisting of several complete sentences be formatted?
- Lowercase with semicolons.
 - Begin with a capital letter and end with a full stop.**⁹
 - Uppercase with commas.
 - Italicized with no punctuation.
10. What is the correct way to write contractions in British usage?
- With a full stop (e.g., Mr.).
 - Without a full stop (e.g., Mr).**¹⁰
 - With an apostrophe (e.g., Mr').
 - In all capital letters (e.g., MR).

⁸ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 8th ed. (European Commission, 2021), 48.

⁹ Ibid., 59.

¹⁰ Ibid., 44.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 5th ed. Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2024.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.